

REDEFINING VARIANCE TESTING: EXPLORING ALTERNATIVE APPROACHES

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Abstract: *Levene's Test, as introduced by, offers a method for assessing variability within a population. It involves calculating the absolute differences between individual values (x) and their group mean (\bar{x}), followed by conducting a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on these derived values. This test provides a valuable tool for investigating the homogeneity of variances among different groups, a fundamental aspect in statistical analysis.*

Keywords: *Levene's Test, variability, population, one-way ANOVA, homogeneity.*

Development of Test Statistic

For a value from population, Levene's Test [4] proposes $= | - \bar{ } |$ and conducting one-way ANOVA on the subsequent values.

As a variation on the above transformation, I propose $(- \bar{ })$

The sample mean of this quantity is

$$\frac{\sum(- \bar{ })}{n} = \frac{-1}{n}$$

If we subtract the sample mean from this quantity and divide by, the result is

$$= \frac{(- \bar{ }) - \frac{-1}{n}}{n} = \frac{(- \bar{ }) - \frac{-1}{n}}{n}$$

If a vector is multiplied by a constant, then and are also multiplied by :

$$\frac{(- \bar{ }) - \frac{-1}{n}}{n} = \frac{(- \bar{ }) - \frac{-1}{n}}{n}$$

$$= \frac{(- \bar{ }) - \frac{-1}{n}}{n} =$$

Thus, is also multiplied by. Another property of is that

$$\lim_{\rightarrow} | | = 0 \text{ and } \lim_{\rightarrow} | | = \infty$$

This property of allows us to use standard nonparametric ranking tests to test hypotheses of one or more variances: One variance: Wilcoxon signed ranks test [6]

Two variances: Wilcoxon rank sum test

Three or more variances: Kruskal-Wallis test [3]

The requirement for two or more variances is that the samples are independent. The minimum scale for all tests is ordinal. Each sample size needs to be at least 3.

One Variance

Given the hypothesized standard deviation, we modify as

$$= \frac{(- \bar{ }) - \frac{-1}{n}}{n}$$

If $\sigma > 0$ then

$$\frac{(-)}{(-)} > \frac{-1}{-1}$$

$$(-) > \frac{-1}{-1}$$

From this

$$< - \frac{-1}{-1}$$

or

$$> - + \frac{-1}{-1}$$

Given the alternative hypothesis $\sigma > 0$, as $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$, the range for σ decreases, signifying an increase in σ and a decrease in σ , making it less likely to reject the null hypothesis. Conversely, as $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, the range for σ increases, signifying a decrease in σ and an increase in σ , making it more likely to reject the null hypothesis.

If $\sigma < 0$ then

$$\frac{(-)}{(-)} < \frac{-1}{-1}$$

$$(-) < \frac{-1}{-1}$$

From this

$$- \frac{-1}{-1} < - + \frac{-1}{-1}$$

Given the alternative hypothesis $\sigma < 0$, as $\sigma \rightarrow 0$, the range for σ decreases, signifying a decrease in σ and an increase in σ , making it less likely to reject the null hypothesis. Conversely, as $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$, the range for σ increases, signifying an increase in σ and a decrease in σ , making it more likely to reject the null hypothesis.

Example 1

Given the data set $X = \{4,5,5,5,6,6,9,10\}$, $\bar{X} = 6.25$ and $s = 2.1213$.

Test the hypothesis $\sigma = 1.5$ versus $\sigma > 1.5$ at a 5% level of significance.

We reject the null hypothesis if $T \leq 6$

The following table summarizes the results:

X	Q	Rank Q
4	2.0625	6
5	- 0.27083	2
5	- 0.27083	2
5	- 0.27083	2
6	-1.27083	4.5
6	-1.27083	4.5
9	3.729167	7
10	8.0625	8

= 15. Do not reject the null hypothesis and conclude σ is not greater than 1.5 at a 5% level of significance.

A normality test using Lilliefors [5] indicates that assumptions of normality are not satisfied.

Test the hypothesis $\sigma = 0.5$ versus $\sigma > 0.5$ at a 5% level of significance.

The following table summarizes the results:

X	Q	Rank Q
4	9.6875	6
5	2.6875	4
5	2.6875	4
5	2.6875	4
6	-0.3125	1.5
6	-0.3125	1.5
9	14.6875	7
10	27.6875	8

= 3. Reject the null hypothesis and conclude σ is greater than 0.5 at a 5% level of significance.

Two variances

We modify for each sample as:

$$= \frac{(-)}{-1}$$

Example 2

Given these two data sets:

Group 1	102.7	99.9	104.4	98.7	99	99.5	98.6	99.4
Group 2	103.4	112.6	100.1	111.7	108	100.1	80	98.1

Their respective means are 100.275 and 101.75 and their respective variances are 4.4736 and 107.1914.

A proposed hypothesis = versus < at a 5% level of significance.

We reject the null hypothesis if ≤ 52 where represents the rank sum of Group 1. The following table summarizes the results:

Group 1	Group 2	Q1	Q2	RQ1	RQ2
102.7	103.4	0.929633	8.796204	4	14
99.9	112.6	1.78421	2.311334	8	9
104.4	100.1	6.194205	8.796204	11	14
98.7	111.7	0.67787	0.50322	3	1
99	108	1.082109	5.286222	5	10
99.5	100.1	1.566724	8.796204	7	14
98.6	80	0.524211	36.63266	2	16
99.4	98.1	1.488713	7.772379	6	12

The rank sum of Group 1 is 46. Reject the null hypothesis and conclude < . The p-value for the test is 1.03%. Conducting the above test using Levene’s test, the test statistic is 5.27 with a p-value of 3.8%. Conducting the Anderson-Darling normality test [1] on Group 1, the p-value is 1.6%.

Three variances

The value of is computed for each sample in the same manner as for two variances.

Example 3

Given these groups of data:

Group 1	102.7	99.9	104.4	98.7	99	99.5	98.6	99.4
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Group 2	103.4	112.6	100.1	111.7	108	100.1	80	98.1
Group 3	103.4	112.6	100.1	101.7	108	100.1	90	98.1

Is there a significant difference in the variances of at least two groups?

Groups 1 and 2 are the same groups used in Example 2. Group 3 is virtually identical to Group 2 with 80 being changed to 90 and 111.7 to 101.7 in order to create a data set with less variation than Group 2. We reject the null hypothesis if the test statistic is greater than 5.991. The following table summarizes the results:

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Q1	Q2	Q3	RQ1	RQ2	RQ3
102.7	103.4	103.4	0.929633	8.796204	5.477164	5	20	14
99.9	112.6	112.6	1.78421	2.311334	11.62968	9	10	22
104.4	100.1	100.1	6.194205	8.796204	5.477164	17	20	14
98.7	111.7	101.7	0.67787	0.50322	5.881778	4	2	16
99	108	108	1.082109	5.286222	0.071402	6	12	1
99.5	100.1	100.1	1.566724	8.796204	5.477164	8	20	14
98.6	80	90	0.524211	36.63266	14.65536	3	24	23
99.4	98.1	98.1	1.488713	7.772379	3.90036	7	18	11

The rank sums are 59, 126, and 115 respectively. The value of the test statistic is 6.455 which have a p-value of 3.97%. We reject the null hypothesis and conclude a significant difference in the variances of at least two groups. The Hartley test [2] produces a test statistic of 23.96. Based on an F distribution with 7 and 7 degrees of freedom, the p-value is 0.02%. However, given the p-value of 1.6% on Group 1 from the Anderson-Darling normality test, the results of the Hartley test are suspect.

As seen in Example 2, we know that the variance of Group 1 is significantly less than that of Group 2. Given the alternative hypothesis $\sigma_1 < \sigma_2$, here are the results:

Group 1	Group 3	Q1	Q3	RQ1	RQ3
102.7	103.4	0.929633	5.477164	4	11
99.9	112.6	1.78421	11.62968	8	15
104.4	100.1	6.194205	5.477164	14	11
98.7	101.7	0.67787	5.881778	3	13
99	108	1.082109	0.071402	5	1
99.5	100.1	1.566724	5.477164	7	11
98.6	90	0.524211	14.65536	2	16
99.4	98.1	1.488713	3.90036	6	9

We reject the null hypothesis if $S_1 \leq 52$ where represents the rank sum of Group 1. The rank sum of Group 1 is 49. We reject the null hypothesis and conclude $\sigma_1 < \sigma_2$.

Given the alternative hypothesis $\sigma_2 > \sigma_3$, here are the results:

Group 2	Group 3	Q2	Q3	RQ2	RQ3
103.4	103.4	8.796204	5.443258	12	6
112.6	112.6	2.311334	11.85861	3	14

100.1	100.1	8.796204	5.516848	12	7.5
111.7	101.1	0.50322	5.836482	2	9
108	108	5.286222	0.061883	5	1
100.1	100.1	8.796204	5.516848	12	7.5
80	90	36.63266	14.37852	16	15
98.1	98.1	7.772379	3.985578	10	4

We reject the null hypothesis if ≥ 84 where represents the rank sum of Group 2. The rank sum of Group 2 is 72. We do not reject the null hypothesis and conclude the variance of Group 2 is not significantly greater than that of Group 3.

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